

Wheat landraces for the win

Introducing a treasure trove of beneficial traits for the development of “super” cultivars

Wheat landraces are unique in that they are well suited for cultivation under sub-optimal conditions

The combination of rapidly increasing world population, decline in the amount and quality of arable land and increase in climate catastrophes as a result of climate change warrants progressive research on strategies to secure food supply for the populace. Cereals form an integral constituent of the human diet, and one of the oldest and most important cereal crops is wheat. To ensure that sufficient wheat is produced to feed the projected global population of 9 billion in 2050, there is a need to improve wheat productivity from the current 3 tonnes per hectare to 5 t/ha. This must be achieved in the midst of the uncertain biotic and abiotic factors imposed by future climate change scenarios. One strategy to achieve elevated wheat yields under undesirable conditions is to “learn” and “adapt” age-old secrets from cultivars of the past that were able

to thrive under sub-optimal conditions. Breeding strategies which employed the introduction of dwarfing genes resulted in a drastic increase in wheat yields, under optimal environmental conditions, during the green revolution. However, such elite varieties are less resilient to unfavourable conditions, whereas landraces are unique in that they are well suited for cultivation under sub-optimal conditions.

What are landraces?

Landraces refer to traditional varieties of wheat with elevated capacities to tolerate abiotic and biotic stresses such as drought and insect pests, respectively. In general, landraces are genetically diverse, well adapted to local conditions, are mostly associated with traditional farming systems and have not been exposed to formal crop improvement like elite cultivars. Landraces have been developed naturally or by farmer-mediated selections that resulted in the generation of plants with the capability to thrive under local climatic or environmental

conditions. This ability has resulted in landraces being considered important reservoirs of useful genes that code for adaptation traits which enable them to thrive under less desirable conditions.

With this treasure trove of adaptation traits, why are climate-resilient landraces not cultivated instead of elite cultivars? Whilst wheat landraces have greater tolerance to biotic and abiotic stress, the yield obtained is lower than with modern, elite cultivars. Hence, the latter are preferred for cultivation on a large scale. This leaves us in a Catch-22 situation.

How then do we achieve the best of both worlds in terms of optimal wheat yields even under sub-optimal conditions? This may be achieved by breeding ‘super’ cultivars with genes encoding stress tolerance as well as yield optimization.

Strategies for utilization of landraces in wheat breeding

Wheat landraces are considered a promising resource for breeders not only due to their

multitude of desirable traits but also due to the ease of breeding with wheat landraces since they form constituents of the primary gene pool. Moreover, the conservation and collection of a large number of landraces ensures that we have a rich reserve of these resources that may be utilized in the breeding process. Landraces may be utilized in wheat improvement programmes by using them as either a donor or recipient. As a donor, traits from landraces may be bred into elite varieties, while as a recipient, landrace yield potential may be improved by integrating yield traits from elite cultivars into promising landrace cultivars. For breeding programmes using landraces to be successful, several strategies need to be in place such as forming core collections where genetic diversity is maximized and allele mining for key traits of interest to enrich the genetic diversity.

Protecting landraces

There is a growing need to protect landraces considering their rich genetic variability and abundance of beneficial traits, which are of increasing importance due to the rise in environmental stressors bombarding wheat as climate change intensifies. Landraces have long been recognized as treasure troves of genetic material that may be key to securing food resources for future generations.

Conservation of these rich gene pools requires the concerted effort of national

and international programmes. Moreover, concerted effort is required to increase in situ conservation of landraces and to appropriately manage and log data on collected landraces in a secure, global data repository.

A well maintained landrace collection may serve as a stepping stone for breeders to efficiently develop 'super' climate-resilient, high yielding wheat cultivars. This repository could be the key to solving food security problems whereby knowledge of the past may provide a saving grace for the future.

WISH-ROOTS project and partners

A recently initiated project titled "Tuning the wheat root microbiome to improve soil health and optimize rhizosphere nitrogen cycling and availability (WISH-ROOTS)" aims at restoring and preserving soil health through wheat root traits. International research consortium partners from the United Kingdom, Italy, South Africa, China, Germany, Belgium and Spain are currently growing 20 landrace cultivars of bread and durum wheat on fields in their respective countries, and evaluating the effect of the different cultivars on soil microbiome dynamics and nitrogen cycling. Overall, the project anticipates to provide advantageous cultivars for farmers that support a more sustainable use of land, by reintroducing the positive traits of the landrace, thereby improving soil microbial biodiversity and structure, as well as nutrient cycling.

The WISH-ROOTS project is funded by the European Joint Programme Soil ERA-NET (HORIZON 2020) and the New Zealand Government to support the objectives of the Global Research Alliance on Agricultural Greenhouse Gases (GRA).

The Agricultural Research Council (ARC) is leading the South African component of the project. ■

For more information: Visit the WISH-ROOTS website: <https://www.wishroots-ejpsol.net/>

and social media page: https://twitter.com/wish_roots

or contact: Dr Ashira Roopnarain; e-mail: RoopnarainA@arc.agric.za

Dr Busiswa Ndaba; e-mail: NdabaB@arc.agric.za

Mr Michael Kidson; e-mail: Michael@arc.agric.za

Dr Buhlebelive Mndzebele; e-mail: MndzebeleB@arc.agric.za

ARC-Natural Resources and Engineering (NRE) and Vegetable, Industrial and Medicinal Plants (VIMP)

Nampo Cape

13 - 16 Sept 2023

NATION IN CONVERSATION

The conversation continues...

◆ Trade relations under scrutiny: The economic impact of the Russian war in South Africa

13/09

◆ Unlocking potential: Growth in the canola industry of the Cape

◆ The Cape at the helm: Progress with power generation

14/09

◆ From livestock to benefit: Challenges of the sheep industry's value chain in the Cape Province

FOLLOW US ON THESE PLATFORMS

Facebook: [NationinConversation](#)

Instagram: [nationconverse](#)

YouTube: [NasieinGesprekNationinConversation](#)

Twitter: [NationConverse](#)

Web: www.nasieingesprek.co.za

REMEMBER: Each conversation will be streamed live from **Facebook** and **YouTube**

